

REPORT:

A1.3.5: Gaps in microfluidic flow control methodologies

Work package 1

<https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written as part of activity A1.3.5 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

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1. Scope

This report (A1.3.5) was preceded by activity A1.3.4, which compiled information on subjects such as flow control ranges, existing metrology, existing standards, and calibration protocols within microfluidics and other industries (such as pharmaceutical, food and petrol). That work was an input to this report, which aims to identify gaps in microfluidic flow control methodologies, and if there is a need for new guidelines for implementing existing flow control protocols and standards to microfluidics.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.3.5 M30	Using input from A1.3.4, DTI, CETIAT, IPQ, EnablingMNT and CMI will identify the gaps in microfluidic control flow methodologies, and will assess the need for the development of new guidelines for the implementation of existing protocols and standards for flow control to microfluidics.	DTI , CETIAT, IPQ, EnablingMNT, CMI

2. Existing flow control methodology

The sections below present existing flow control methodology by reviewing and discussing selected reports of the MFMET project and selected academic literature.

2.1. Flow control in MFMET reports

Kartmann et al. discuss various aspects of flow control in microfluidics, and they identify three main categories of flow control: passive control, active flow control, and feedback flow control (Kartmann et al., 2023).

Passive flow control functions via geometry, surface properties, or material properties of microchannels to control the flow. Examples of such geometries in microchannels are pillars and grooves, examples of surface properties are hydrophobic or hydrophilic, and an example of a material property is porosity.

Active flow control functions via application of external actuators to adjust the flow. Piezoelectric actuators, microvalves, and electromagnetic fields are examples of such external actuators.

Feedback flow control use sensors to monitor the flow, and such sensors give input to a feedback control system that adjusts the flow according to a preset target. The preset target is sometimes referred to as a setpoint. Two examples of sensor types are pressure sensors or flow sensors, an example of a feedback control system is the proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller, and examples of adjustable flow generators are pressure driven flow generators and syringe pumps. Integrated systems are commercially available, and such a system encompass a complete set of feedback flow control elements such as a sensor, a controller, and a flow generator.

Further discussions of existing flow control technologies, such as pumps, pressure sources, flow sensors, pressure sensors, and valves can be found in another report by Kartmann et al. (Kartmann et al., 2022). Furthermore, the report by Akselli et al. presents a list of flow metrology terms and definitions (Akselli et al., 2022), and a discussion of various methods for flow rate measurements is available in the report by Copeland et al. (Copeland et al., 2023). The report by Daugbjerg et el. discuss

several methods for leakage testing in microfluidics: visual inspection, pressure decay, and flow rate (Daugbjerg et al., 2023).

2.2. Flow control in papers and review papers

Kartmann et al. presents a list of several papers and review papers and a selection of these are discussed below (Kartmann et al., 2023):

The report by Morgan et al. was written as a part of the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery (MeDD II) project (Morgan et al., 2020). This text is limited to Newtonian liquids, and it defines the quantity *response or delay time*. The report describes calibration methods for measuring the response or delay time of drug delivery devices for flow rates in the range 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min. It then presents the flow rate calibration facilities of the 9 institutions which are partnering the report. The report also describes uncertainty calculations for flow rate calibration with the gravimetric method, the optical method (front track), the displacement method, and microfluidic Particle Imaging Velocimetry (microPIV). The report was then published as a paper in Biomedical Engineering special issue in 2022 on “Medical flow and dosing measurement metrology in drug delivery” (Batista et al., 2023).

A comparison on different calibration methods of syringe pumps and flow meters was also performed by several National Metrology Laboratories in 2022, and the report from this comparison has the title: EURAMET Project 1508 - Pilot study: Intercomparison of ultra-low liquid flow rates in range below 100 nL/min (NEL et al., 2022). The results can be found in the correspondent [report](#), and most of the calibration results are in agreement with the reference value.

The paper by Bissig et al. describes primary standards for measuring flow rates from 100 nL/min to 1 mL/min (Bissig et al., 2015). It explains the principle of flow rate calibration with the gravimetric method, and it features 6 implementations of such calibration facilities at the 6 institutions that are partnering the paper. Finally, the paper presents results from an intercomparison of flow rate calibration, where most of the calibration results are in agreement with the reference value. See Bissig et al. for further details (Bissig et al., 2015).

The paper by Cioncolini et al. discuss measurement and prediction of the pressure drop across micro-orifices in microfluidic systems (Cioncolini et al., 2015). The study is motivated by improving design and operation of microfluidics systems, via a better understanding of fluid mechanical phenomena at the micro-scale. The paper introduces other studies working with orifices, various fluid mechanical characteristics of orifices, and the paper presents its experimental orifice setup. The results present various paired measurements of dimensionless pressure drop and Reynolds numbers. These results are discussed in relation to different prediction models applicable within different ranges of Reynolds numbers, e.g., flow regimes such as creeping flow and turbulence. Provided that prediction methods stay within their applicable flow regime, the predictions were found to agree with the measurements.

Akselli & Teke present a paper investigating binning of pixels from a Charged Coupled Device (CCD) in Particle Imaging Velocimetry (PIV) of laminar flow in a microchannel (Akselli & Teke, 2011). PIV is a non-invasive optical measuring technique for determining fluid motion. It is highlighted that PIV for microfluidics (microPIV) differs from normal PIV by having different approaches to illumination of the flow. The study presents data analysis for vertical pixel binning (vertical PB) for CCD cameras in microPIV, and data analyses for obtaining velocity vector profiles from CCD images and seeding particles. Finally, Akselli & Teke conclude that the application of microPIV successfully determined flow velocity profiles, and that vertical PB offers new possibilities for increasing the spatial resolution and the dynamic velocity range of the measurements (Akselli & Teke, 2011).

Batista et al. present the development of microflow measurement using interferometry (Batista et al., 2020). The study is motivated by a need to expand measurement capabilities of flow rate to smaller values, for example closer to 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$. The experimental setup comprises an interferometer system with a laser unit, an optical detector, and two retroreflector cubes where one of them has a beam splitter. The retroreflector cube without the beam splitter is mounted on the pusher block of a syringe pump, and thus moves with the syringe plunger when the syringe pump generates a flow. With this interferometer setup, the optical detector sees an interference pattern with bright and dark fringes that changes as the syringe plunger moves. The change through a whole fringe pattern cycle, for example from a bright fringe through a dark fringe back to a bright fringe, corresponds to the syringe plunger having moved one integer wavelength of the laser light, e.g., 633 nm. Thus, the movement of the syringe plunger can be monitored with sub-micrometre precision. Further quantities such as syringe radius and time are important for flow rate measurement with interferometry, and Batista et al. present an uncertainty budget for the interferometry method (Batista et al., 2020). The study validates the interferometry method by comparing with gravimetric flow rate calibration. Batista et al. conclude that the results from the two methods are in agreement, and for small flow rates (e.g., 0.01 mL/h) the interferometry method has smaller uncertainties than the gravimetric method (Batista et al., 2020).

Ogheard et al. present the development of an optical method for liquid volume measurement in the microlitre range (Ogheard et al., 2020). This development is motivated by a need for accurate determination of volume in the microlitre range, and this need is associated with characterization of activity per volume for radiopharmaceuticals in nuclear medicine. Ogheard et al. continue and present the developed system and its subcomponents (Ogheard et al., 2020). Without conveying all details, the system operates by immersing a clean and empty capillary into the liquid sample and subsequently lifting the capillary out of the liquid. The capillary now contains a sampled volume of the liquid. A syringe pump applies suction to move the sampled volume up the capillary, so it is defined by two menisci. A camera captures images of the sampled volume, and the volume of the sampled volume is determined using a series of steps regarding image processing, data analyses, and corrections. The capillary is then moved, and the sampled volume has its activity measured by a dedicated activity measurement system. Thereby, activity by volume has been determined, and the process is finished. Furthermore, Ogheard et al. present an uncertainty budget for the optical volume measurement, along with validation of the method via comparison with mass measurement using a calibrated balance (Ogheard et al., 2020). The results present volume measurements for 0.2 μL and 1 μL with relative standard uncertainty 2 % ($k=2$), and Ogheard et al. conclude that there is agreement between the volume measurements and mass measurements.

The white paper by van Heeren et al. discuss many aspects of leakage testing in microfluidics (van Heeren et al., 2022). The document aims to serve as a guideline and introduce a roadmap for the testing of microfluidic devices, and much of its focus is on leakage testing. The white paper presents a Failure Mode and Effect Analysis (FMEA), and several common microfluidic leakage test methods: visual inspection, liquid pressure drop, and gas pressure drop. It also discusses burst pressure testing, and it categorizes leakage testing according to several parameters: chemical hazards, temperature, pressure, risk to the user, capillary flow, and needs arising the intended use of the device. The white paper gives advice for the future development of leakage testing protocols, and it ends with a series of questions that may be answered by future developments in microfluidic leakage testing. One of these questions interestingly asks: what is the quantitative and qualitative relation between the leakage of gas and liquid in microfluidic devices? Answers to this question might enable using gas testing methods to devices intended for use with liquid, and gas testing is considered non-contaminating, non-destructive, and sensitive (van Heeren et al., 2022).

3. Defined target for flow control

The report by Geršl et al. presents quantitative parameters for flow control in microfluidics, and these are presented in Table 1 (Geršl et al., 2023). This report uses these values and parameters to define the target for flow control.

Table 1: Typical parameters for flow control in microfluidics. This report uses these values to define the target of flow control. Parameters and values quoted from Geršl et al. (Geršl et al., 2023).

Parameter	Most common range
Flow rate	10 nL/min – 1 mL/min
Accuracy of flow control	< 5 %
Dynamic viscosity of media	$1 \cdot 10^{-3}$ Pa·s – $5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ Pa·s
Temperature	4 °C – 50 °C
Pressure	< 2 bar

The report by Geršl et al. also presents the most common pump technologies used in microfluidic flow control: syringe pumps, pressurised reservoirs, peristaltic pumps, and capillary flow-based systems (Geršl et al., 2023). For syringe pumps, pressurised reservoirs, and peristaltic pumps further information is available in the report by Kartmann et al. such as market availability, flow rate range, and accuracy (Kartmann et al., 2022). Further information on capillary pressure control valves is available in the review by Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2021).

4. Existing standardisation

The report by Geršl et al. lists several guidelines, protocols, standards, and technical reports related to flow control in microfluidics (Geršl et al., 2023). These documents are listed below, and a short description of their contents was compiled and quoted from their abstracts. In the below, an infusion pump is a device to administer a liquid medicament with high viscosity through small catheters to the veins of a patient.

4.1. Pharmaceutical and laboratory

- *IEC 60601-2-24 Medical electrical equipment – Part 2-24: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of infusion pumps and controllers (TC 62/SC 62D, 2012)*

This standard addresses the basic safety and essential performance of infusion pumps and volumetric infusion controllers. The standard covers requirements and performance tests for enteral nutrition pumps, infusion pumps, infusion pumps for ambulatory use, syringe or container pumps, volumetric infusion controllers, and volumetric infusion pumps. Here enteral refers to the human gastrointestinal tract. The standard cautions that it does not cover other aspects of drug administration, and not the following types of devices: extracorporeal circulation of blood, implantable devices, equipment specifically intended for diagnostic use within urodynamics, equipment specifically intended for diagnostic use within male impotence testing, and devices covered by ISO 28620.

- *AAMI TIR101:2021, Fluid delivery performance testing for infusion pumps* (AAMI, 2021)

This technical report addresses requirements, instrumentation, and procedures for test methods for fluid delivery performance, and the report covers the full range of use conditions for an infusion pump. The aim of the test is to give clinically relevant data for the performance of the pump. The technical report applies to syringe pumps, container pumps, and volumetric infusion pumps for the indicated delivery modes, including enteral, patient-controlled analgesia (PCA), or epidural and prescribed infusate sources. Here analgesia refers to pain relief, and epidural refers to the epidural space in the anatomy of the human spine. The technical report cautions that it does not address uncertainty of measurement, nor does it establish criteria for the clinical acceptability of infusion pump performance or validation of test methods.

- *IPQ, Metrology in Health – Good Practice Guide, Part II, Chapter III – Infusion Pumps, 2018* (CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018)

This good practice guide for infusion pumps addresses infusion pumps for the purpose of administering drugs to the human body. The guide describes and characterises several types of pumps: volumetric infusion pumps, peristaltic pumps, syringe pumps, and elastomeric pumps. Also described is flow rate calibration of pumps using the gravimetric method, and good practises for maintenance and handling of infusion pumps.

- *ISO 28620:2020 Medical devices – Non-electrically driven portable infusion devices* (ISO/TC 76, 2020)

This standard specifies requirements and test methods for non-electrically driven portable infusion devices. It is applicable for devices designed for continuous flow and/or for bolus neuraxial and intravascular or hypodermic application. Here bolus refers to the administration of a discrete amount of drug (volume quantity) within a specific time, neuraxial refers to the epidural space or intrathecal space in the anatomy of the human spine, intravascular refers to the space of a blood vessel, and hypodermic refers to the space under the skin. Various scenarios are relevant for the portable infusion devices: The devices can be administered by a health care professional or the patient. The devices can be filled by the manufacturer, a health care professional, or the patient. The standard warns that it is not applicable to electrically driven or controlled infusions pumps that are covered by IEC 60601-2-24, devices for single patient use covered by ISO 11608 series, implantable devices, enteral devices, transdermal delivery devices, and devices where the energy for infusion is not provided by the device or active intervention by the patient.

- *ISO 7886-2:2020, Sterile hypodermic syringes for single use – Part 2: Syringes for use with power-driven syringe pumps* (ISO/TC 84, 2020)

This standard specifies requirements for the following subset of sterile single-use hypodermic syringes: Syringes with capacity 1 mL or more, made of plastic, and for use with a power-driven syringe pump. It specifies the requirements for performance of short-term flow rate accuracy, pump force and syringe compliance. The standard warns that it is not applicable to syringes with auto-disposable features covered by ISO 7886-3, syringes for use with insulin covered by ISO 8537, glass syringes for single-use, syringes prefilled with the injection, and syringes supplied with injection for filling by a

pharmacist. Furthermore, the standard does not cover the compatibility of syringes and injection fluids.

- *ISO 8655-9: 2022 - Piston-operated volumetric apparatus - Part 9: Manually operated precision laboratory syringes (ISO/TC 48, 2022)*

This standard specifies requirements for manually operated precision laboratory syringes made of glass and metal from 0.1 μL to 200 mL. Part 6 of this series of standards describes the calibration method, instrumentation, and conditions for this type of instrument, based on the gravimetric principle. Furthermore, the standard does not cover the compatibility of syringes and injection fluids.

4.2. Oil industry

- *ASTM D7996-15 Standard Test Method for Measuring Visible Spectrum of Asphaltenes in Heavy Fuel Oils and Crude Oils by Spectroscopy in a Microfluidic Platform (ASTM, 2016)*

This standard describes a microfluidic technique for measuring the visible spectrum of asphaltenes in crude oils and petroleum products. The technique is rapid, and it can be used as a quality control for fuel or crude oil. The visible spectrum of asphaltenes is sensitive to the concentration of asphaltenes, and the technique is intended for samples with asphaltenes mass concentrations below 15 %. The standard covers the measurement made with microfluidics and spectrographic techniques, and it cautions that it does not cover safety concerns and regulatory limitations.

4.3. Biology and chemistry

- *Prabhu, G.R.D., Yang, TH., Hsu, CY. et al., Facilitating chemical and biochemical experiments with electronic microcontrollers and single-board computers, Nature Protocols 15, 925–990 (2020) (Prabhu et al., 2020)*

This protocol addresses using microcontroller boards and single-board computers in the context of chemistry and biochemistry. It presents seven examples of procedures for laboratory routines: (i) Injection of microliter-volume liquid plugs into microscale capillaries. (ii) Transfer of liquid extract to a mass spectrometer. (iii) Liquid-gas extraction of volatile organic compounds (fizzy extraction). (iv) Monitoring experimental conditions over the Internet cloud in real time. (v) Transfer of analytes to a mass spectrometer via a liquid micro-junction, data acquisition, and data deposition into the Internet cloud. (vi) Feedback control of a biochemical reaction. (vii) Optimization of sample flow rate in direct-infusion mass spectrometry.

- *Huh, D., Kim, H., Fraser, J. et al., Microfabrication of human organs-on-chips, Nature Protocols 8, 2135–2157 (2013) (Huh et al., 2013)*

Organs-on-chips are devices of microfluid systems containing living human cells and replicate key functional units of living organs. These microfluidic devices can test drugs, chemicals, and create in vitro models of human disease. Organs-on-chips have the potential to present low-cost alternatives to conventional animal models for pharmaceutical, chemical, and environmental testing. This protocol describes the fabrication and operation of an example microfluidic organs-on-chips system. The

example covers a 'breathing' lung-on-a-chip that mimics the living human lung. The example can be adopted to other human organ chips, for example a gut-on-a-chip.

5. Gaps in microfluidic flow control methodologies

The below sections discuss and identify the gaps in microfluidic flow control methodologies.

5.1. Definition of gaps

This report assumes that the domain of microfluidic flow control methodology is sufficiently covered by the references discussed in section 2 and section 3, i.e., the selected MFMET reports and academic literature. It also assumes that the existing standardisation for microfluidic flow control is sufficiently covered by the literature quoted in section 4, i.e., the selected protocols, guidelines, standards, and technical reports. Furthermore, this report takes the viewpoint that gaps in microfluidic flow control methodology are defined by the topics in microfluidic flow control methodology, which are not covered by the existing standardisation.

Thus, the existing standardisation is evaluated in section 5.2 and section 5.3 with emphasis on relevance for microfluidic flow control methodology. Section 5.4 evaluates the flow control methodology and defined target for flow control, with emphasis on topics not covered by the existing standardisation. Finally, section 5.5 presents the identified gaps.

5.2. Existing standardisation with limited relevance

Section 4.2 discuss a standard from the oil industry. Here, the standard ASTM D7996-15 addresses a spectrographic method for sample characterization in the oil industry (ASTM, 2016). This standard is likely too specific and too focused on its application to be useful as guidelines or standardisation for microfluidic flow control.

Section 4.1 describes pharmaceutical and laboratory standards, and here the standard ISO 8655-9:2022 addresses syringes made of glass and metal used for laboratory purposes (ISO/TC 48, 2022). Syringes are an important mechanical component in syringe pumps, and the abstract of this standard suggests a focus on this component. I.e., the focus of this standard is elsewhere than microfluidic flow control.

In section 4.1, the standard ISO 28620:2020 applies only to non-electrically driven portable infusion devices, which is a subset of devices, and it addresses various medical and clinical applications of infusion devices (ISO/TC 84, 2020). These things considered, this standard appears to have content that is too restricted to contribute to the sought-after generic guidelines or standardisation for microfluidic flow control.

In section 4.1, the standard IEC 60601-2-24:2012 covers basic safety and performance requirements for infusion pumps (TC 62/SC 62D, 2012). It is set in the context of ambulatory use, and it applies to a subset of devices such as syringe pumps and volumetric infusion pumps. Judging from the abstract this standard has an ambulatory and clinical approach to infusion pumps, and it appears to be less useful as guidelines or standardisation for microfluidic flow control.

5.3. Existing standardisation with some relevance

In section 4.3 on biology and chemistry, the protocol by Prabhu et al. addresses microcontroller-controlled laboratory routines such as injection of liquid, transfer of organic compounds, mass spectrometry, and data acquisition to the Internet cloud (Prabhu et al., 2020). These are interesting subjects, but not directly relevant for standardisation of microfluidic flow control. However, Prabhu et al. discuss optimization of sample flow rate in direct-infusion mass spectrometry, which is relevant for microfluidic flow control (Prabhu et al., 2020).

In section 4.3 on biology and chemistry, the protocol by Huh et al. describes the fabrication and operation of a lung-on-a-chip (Huh et al., 2013). This lung-on-a-chip mimics a living lung by having a physiological flow and a cyclic suction, and these flows are relevant for microfluidic flow control. However, it is difficult to tell from the abstract of Huh et al. how detailed the text discusses flow control, and if it is general and rigorous enough to be used as guidelines or support standardisation (Huh et al., 2013).

In section 4.1, the good practice guide for infusion pumps is highly relevant for microfluidic flow control, as it describes several types of infusion pumps and gravimetric calibration of flow rate for infusion pumps (CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018). If one should point to an area where more could be wanted, this good practise guide has limited discussion of flow control components different from infusion devices, such as piezo electric pumps, pressure driven flow generators, flow sensors, pressure sensors, and valves.

In section 4.1 the standard ISO 7886-2:2020 describes syringes for use with power-driven syringe pumps (ISO/TC 84, 2020), and it explains how to determine the performance of short-term flow rate accuracy and this information can be of some relevance in microfluidic flow control.

In section 4.1, the AAMI TIR101 technical report describes test methods for fluid delivery performance of infusion pumps (AAMI, 2021). The report is set in a clinical context and motivated by the specific application of drug delivery. It introduces many terms and definitions relevant for infusion pumps, and it presents testing. Some of this testing, and the associated data analysis, determines flow-rate error and flow variability, which are relevant for microfluidic flow control. Other quantities, such as loading dose or bolus delivery, are to some extent specific for drug delivery, and they may have limited relevance for guidelines and standardisation in generic microfluidic flow control.

5.4. Existing methodology, defined target, and existing standardisation

Comparison of the existing flow control methodology described in section 2.1 and the existing standardisation described in section 4 reveals that the existing standardisation does not address the stated types of flow control: passive flow control, active flow control, and feedback flow control. The existing standardisation in section 4 typically covers infusion devices where the pump could be a syringe pump or a peristaltic pump. Some diffusion pumps discussed in the existing standardisation can be characterized as feedback flow control, while the good practices guide for infusion pumps mentions some simpler pumps without sensors (CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018). Thus, there can be infusion devices in the existing standardisation that do not fit any of the categories: feedback flow control, passive flow control, or active flow control. Furthermore, pressure driven flow generators and piezo electric pumps are scarcely covered by the existing standardisation. Pressure sensors, flow sensors, and valves are used in microfluidic flow control, but these are also scarcely covered by the existing standardisation. The existing standardisation does not have a list similar to the list by Akselli et al. that summarises flow metrology terms and definitions for microfluidic flow control

methodology (Akselli et al., 2022). Also, the existing standardisation does not address microfluidic leakage testing, which for example is discussed in the report by Daugbjerg et al. (Daugbjerg et al., 2023).

This and the following paragraph compare the existing flow control methodology described in section 2.2 and the existing standardisation described in section 4. In section 2.2, the report by Morgan et al. and the paper by Bissig et al. account for flow rate calibration with the gravimetric method (Bissig et al., 2015; Morgan et al., 2020). The report by Morgan et al. has more details on the definition of the response or delay time and uncertainty calculations. In section 4, the good practices guide for infusion pumps, AAMI TIR101 technical report, and ISO 7886-2:2020 also describe flow rate calibration with the gravimetric method (AAMI, 2021; CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018; ISO/TC 84, 2020). Hence, many aspects of flow rate calibration by the gravimetric method are covered by existing standardisation. However, one could argue for the benefits of new standardisation dedicated to microfluidics generators, rather than infusion pumps, and with more details related to system assemblies, components, and measurement instruments. In section 2.2, the paper by Batista et al. discusses measurements of small flow rates close to 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{h}$ using interferometry (Batista et al., 2020), and this flow rate measurement by interferometry methodology is not covered by the existing standardisation discussed in section 4. Also, the optical method (front track) for measuring flow rate discussed in Morgan et al. is not covered by existing standardisation (Morgan et al., 2020). The leakage testing discussed by van Heeren et al. is also not covered by the existing standardisation (van Heeren et al., 2022). In 2023, Van Heeren made a survey of measurement and standardisation priorities in microfluidics, and this survey found that leakage testing is among the highest prioritised issues in microfluidics (van Heeren, 2023). Part of the results of the survey by van Heeren is available in Figure 1 (van Heeren, 2023). Thus, the field of microfluidics has much to gain from new standardisation or guidelines covering dedicated metrological procedures for different quantities, and specially flow control and leakage.

Figure 1: Part of the results from the survey on measurement and standardisation priorities in microfluidics by van Heeren (van Heeren, 2023). The figure shows the answers from about 175 persons in microfluidics asked to prioritise a list of topics within microfluidic metrology. Here, the topic of leakage received the highest priority.

The paper by Cioncolini et al. discusses pressure drop across micro-orifices, and the paper by Akselli & Teke discusses pixel binning in microPIV (Akselli & Teke, 2011; Cioncolini et al., 2015). This report considers these topics out of scope in the context of generic methodology for flow control, and thus they are not discussed further here. The paper by Ogheard et al. deals with determination of volume for sampled micro-volumes of liquid (Ogheard et al., 2020). Volume determination is an important method, but it has limited application for the flow control methodology discussed here, and therefore the paper by Ogheard et al. is not discussed further here.

The defined target for flow control in Table 1 originates from a survey of the field of microfluidics, and Table 2 repeats it for convenience (Geršl et al., 2023). The good practises guide for infusion pumps and the AAMI TIR101 technical report also discuss flow parameters, and Table 2 summarises the ranges of parameters found in these discussions (AAMI, 2021; CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018).

Table 2: The defined target for flow control stated in Table 1 is repeated in this table for convenience. The table also presents a summary of the range of parameters found in the good practices guide and the technical report (AAMI, 2021; CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018). The value used for the dynamic viscosity of the 0.9 % normal saline solution is $1.07 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ (Ko et al., 2022).

Parameter	Defined target (Geršl et al., 2023)	Good practices guide (CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018)	Technical report (AAMI, 2021)
Flow rate	10 nL/min – 1 mL/min	0.1 mL/h – 1200 mL/h (1.7 nL/min – 20 mL/min)	0.01 mL/h – 1200 mL/h (0.17 nL/min – 20 mL/min)
Accuracy of flow control	< 5 %	2 % - 5 %	5 % - 10 %
Dynamic viscosity of media	$1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ – $5 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$	N/A	1.01 – 3.735 Dextrose / Normal Saline Solution (0.9 %) Viscosity Ratio ($1.1 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ – $4.0 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$)
Temperature	4 °C – 50 °C	10 °C – 40 °C	5 °C – 40 °C
Pressure	< 2 bar	103 mmHg – 1034 mmHg (0.14 bar – 1.4 bar)	-100 mmHg – +500 mmHg (-0.1 bar – +0.7 bar)

In Table 2, comparison shows that the defined target flow rate is covered by the good practices guide and technical report (AAMI, 2021; CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018). The defined target for accuracy of flow control is covered by the good practices guide, but not the technical report. The ranges of the defined target for dynamic viscosity, temperature, and pressure are outside the ranges of the good practise guide and technical report. In conclusion, the defined target for flow control is not fully covered by existing standardisation.

5.5. Gaps in microfluidic flow control methodologies

The definition of gaps in microfluidic flow control methodology was stated in section 5.1, and with this definition and the comparisons in sections 5.2, 5.3, and 5.4 the following gaps are identified:

1. A list of flow metrology terms and definitions dedicated to microfluidic flow control, see Akselli et al. (Akselli et al., 2022).
2. A description dedicated to the operation of microfluidic flow control systems. I.e., not a description of an application such as drug delivery or spectroscopic analysis of crude oil.
3. Devices such as pressure sensors, flow sensors, and valves.
4. Passive flow control, active flow control, and feedback flow control.
5. Standardisation of the defined target for flow control, see Table 1.
6. Types of pumps, such as pressure driven flow generators and piezo electric pumps, which are different from the types of pumps commonly used in infusion pumps.
7. Standardisation of procedures, instrumentation, and testing conditions needed for accurate measurements of flow control at nanolitre range using different technologies (interferometry, front track, gravimetric, other), dedicated to microfluidics applications and assemblies.
8. Leakage testing.
9. Qualitative or quantitative relationships between leakage testing with gas and leakage testing with liquid.

6. Guidelines for implementing existing flow control protocols and standards to microfluidics

This report is to assess the need for the development of new guidelines for the implementation of existing protocols and standards for flow control to microfluidics. Section 5.5 identified the gaps in microfluidic flow control methodologies, and these are free from topics that were considered out of scope and removed in section 5.4. Accordingly, this report assesses that the gaps in section 5.5 express a need for new guidelines in microfluidics.

The existing standardisation that is interesting for this need includes the good practices guide for infusion pumps and the technical report AAMI TIR101 (AAMI, 2021; CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018). The good practices guide contains methodologies such as syringe pumps, peristaltic pumps, quantitative requirements for infusion pumps, and flow rate calibration using the gravimetric method (CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018). Among other things, the technical report AAMI TIR101:2021 contains methodology on determination of flow-rate error and flow variability (AAMI, 2021). Several needs could be met by implementing their content on flow control to microfluidics, and by adding content on more types of pumps as stated by gap no. 6, and flow rate calibration dedicated to microfluidics as stated by gap no. 7. Though there is no existing standardisation on flow rate measurement with interferometry and optical method (front track), these methodologies are described by Batista et al. and Morgan et al., respectively (Batista et al., 2020; Morgan et al., 2020).

Moreover, this report assesses that there is little need for implementing the existing standards with limited relevance, see section 5.2. The main challenge for the interaction of these standards and the gaps of this report is that these standards were written with another objective than guiding or standardising microfluidic flow control methodology.

A useful contribution to the field of microfluidics could be the development of guidelines dedicated to flow control in microfluidics based on existing methodology, e.g., the literature in section 2. It could be effective for microfluidics to have its own guidelines on flow control, so practitioners of the field can avoid piecing together multiple subsections distributed throughout multiple texts. One or more guidelines could be made for gaps no. 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 in section 5.5, and these could address operation of flow control systems, devices, terms, definitions, and consensus for a defined target for flow control. Finally, a guideline could address topics of leakage testing as expressed in gap no. 8 and 9,

and a recent survey indicates that such a guideline would be highly sought after by the microfluidics field (van Heeren, 2023).

In conclusion, this report identifies a need for the gaps no. 6 and no. 7 in section 5.5 to be addressed with guidelines for implementing the existing standardisation in the good practices guide for infusion pumps and the technical report AAMI TIR101 (AAMI, 2021; CS/09 – GT1 Metrology in Health, 2018). The gaps no. 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, and 9 are also identified in section 5.5, and some of these could be relevant for the MFMET report A1.3.6 and MFMET deliverable D2, which are to follow this report. The aim of MFMET report A1.3.6 and MFMET deliverable D2 is to develop guidelines for the implementation of consensus-based flow control specification in the microfluidics.

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